

“To Follow or Not to Follow”

Rev. Dr. Michael H. Koplitz

Mark 7:14-21

¹⁴ After He called the crowd to Him again, He *began* saying to them, “Listen to Me, all of you, and understand: ¹⁵ there is nothing outside the man which can defile him if it goes into him; but the things which proceed out of the man are what defile the man. ¹⁶ [“If anyone has ears to hear, let him hear.”] ¹⁷ When he had left the crowd *and* entered the house, His disciples questioned Him about the parable. ¹⁸ And He said to them, “Are you so lacking in understanding also? Do you not understand that whatever goes into the man from outside cannot defile him, ¹⁹ because it does not go into his heart, but into his stomach, and is eliminated?” (*Thus He* declared all foods clean.) ²⁰ And He was saying, “That which proceeds out of the man, that is what defiles the man. ²¹ “For from within, out of the heart of men, proceed the evil thoughts, fornications, thefts, murders, adulteries, ²² deeds of coveting *and* wickedness, *as well as* deceit, sensuality, envy, slander, pride *and* foolishness. ²³ “All these evil things proceed from within and defile the man.”

The LORD gave us His Word as a guide for us to have a spotless life. There are so many rules and regulations that it is virtually impossible to live on Earth and not break a code here and there. The LORD established forgiveness into His system because He was aware that this would indeed happen. What did humans do? They determined which of the Laws they wanted to follow. For example, the Kosher laws were a big problem for Paul when he converted Mithras churches. The pork was cheap and was readily available for meat. How can you tell people to follow the LORD’s Word and eat pork? According to the purity code in Leviticus, pork is off the menu. So the message could be that a person has to decide which of the biblical laws one will follow.

A problem arises when society decides to enact some of its laws instead of the biblical laws. If the new society law or custom is not in violation of anything written in the Bible, then all is good. What happens when the society cannon is against the Bible. For example, today, homosexual attitudes are heavily challenged. Society and culture have determined them to be obsolete, and new regulations in favor of this act are in place. Please take note of the acceptance of the changes not is in question in this writing. Instead, one has to examine these changes and determine whether they violate the tenents of the Bible and if so, does it matter to you? Each person has to decide the answer to that question.

I am sure that there are readers who are upset on both sides of the issue I brought up, especially since I do not answer whether it is biblical or not? I am not going to do that. The mainline denominations have been splitting over the biblical response to the question of homosexuality. The church was already crumbling due to so many other situations internally and externally. Anything that breaks the church apart makes it weaker. The foundation will eventually crack, and Christianity will be eliminated from human history.

Here is a radical idea. Why cannot both sides be correct? Now I am sure some readers are not pleased with this blog. Is it not possible that some of the purity codes in Leviticus were written because of the conditions of the time. For example, people did not cook meat in ancient days. Eating raw pork can kill you. Today everyone knows that! The Kosher law against the eating of pork protected the people from dying. Since we know how to eat pork and not die, is that Kosher law obsolete?

Eating pork becomes a personal choice. If one's canonized Bible includes the Kosher laws on pork; then the answer is no, you cannot eat it. If your canon excludes that Kosher law, then you can eat it. Is ignoring a commandment found in the Bible a strike against your salvation? Pretty doubtful because the LORD worked redemption and forgiveness of sin into the Universe. So why worry?

The bottom line is that each person will have to determine how they will handle the Laws of the Bible. Which do you follow? It is really up to you!!!

May the LORD bless you in your learning and studying of His Word.